

Arts Education as an Important and Powerful Medium in the Teaching Learning Process

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VISUAL ARTS

Encourage speaking, listening, and vocabulary development skills. We can start by introducing elements of lines, colour, and shape. Connecting spoken words (zigzag, sculpture, portrait, etc.) with a visual model helps students grasp new vocabulary. Students share their work and practice their presentation skills.

Clarify thoughts, ideas, and feelings by drawing and labelling.

Art is particularly powerful when it allows students to communicate learning when they cannot express it through writing. It helps in going deeper in units of study. Students can integrate and retain what they are learning in all areas when they have opportunities to create relevant artefacts. Some of the example where the teacher can use arts form as teaching aids are-

1. When teaching science, in the topic cell structure of class 8, the children will find it hard to understand the abstract concept only through lecture, but when it is taught while using picture the children may be able to understand it and when taught using models they understand better.
2. While teaching history the teacher uses pictures or videos such as documentaries on Mughal Empire, Mahabharat, Sakuntala etc., for class 10. The difficult lesson can be made easy through this using method of teaching process to the children.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to show how art education is an important medium in the teaching learning process. The Arts Education is unique tools to stimulate and enrich learning and an integral part of a complete, successful and quality Education. This may help in the foundation of balanced creative, cognitive, emotional, aesthetics and social development of children, youth and life-long learner

KEYWORDS: Art Education, Visual Art, Create a tableau, Dance and Music

INTRODUCTION

Arts education helps make learning matter to students by giving them a medium to connect new knowledge to personal experiences and express what they have learned to others. The art are hands-on, has immediate rewards, focuses on positive achievements, develops concrete products and fosters collaboration. The arts provide many opportunities for students to demonstrate their skills through authentic performance. The arts enable children to grow in confidence and learn how to think positively about themselves and learning.

As students learn to read notes, compose music, play an instrument, memorize dance steps, create a painting, and act in a drama, they are also learning how to develop new concepts, build vocabulary and understand a new language.

Some of the Important ways in which we can use arts as powerful medium in teaching and learning process are-

Fig. Cell structure figure

Fig. Cell structure model

DRAMA

Encourage role playing. Students are able to better understand a story, character, or even if they are able to physically act it out. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are part of the process, but all students can participate. For English learners, use pictures and retell the story orally, while they act it out physically. Students can work collaboratively to write their own stories and act them out for friends.

For example in the "hot seat" to understand character. Students take on the role of a character (fictional or real) and sit in the "hot seat," where they answer the questions of a curious public. Students ask the wolf, "Why did you eat the little pigs?" They question Ruby Bridges, "Were you scared when people yelled at you when you walked to school each day?"

Create a tableau. Even young students can develop a still, silent performance from a scene in a story or representing an event in text, developing a fuller understanding about life and literature. In this way each student is made to participate and thereby making the class an interactive and enjoyable one.

DANCE

Little steps as to develop the expressions of dance can be developed with the students. Focus here is on the movements of body to reflect the sun's gentle warmth /rage of the sun and the students performing the ritual of worship of sun with graceful movements. Let the students create a sun dance, using any combination of soft movements, sharp / graceful or yogic combinations. Add formations to bring more motion and placements giving each child to come in front and demonstrate his talent Create a dance journey from the moods and emotions of sun to the effect of the sun on the earth and it's inhabitants and further to the worship of the sun and then to a request to Sun God for the strength from the sun through the yogic exercises of Surya namaskar.

Movement and Freeze: This is a fun and simple way to incorporate dance movements (skip, twirl, gallop, etc.) as students learn about historical figures, characters, and events.

The teacher can organise a dance competition on various themes such Human Rights Education; to introduce the Human Rights Declaration to young people in an experiential way.

MUSIC, SONG & PERFORMANCE

Sing the concepts. When teacher Want to teach students to clean up, learn grammar, or grasp math facts, they can sing for clean-up, to learn grammar, and math facts too. There are songs for nearly every concept we want to teach. We can make up a song using a familiar tune, or find one online. Songs help students learn and retain information, develops listening skills, and teach tone, beat, and rhythm. Singing songs and rhymes teaches English learners how language is constructed and helps with acquisition of English.

One common example is teaching of rhymes in children uses body movement, gesture and rhythmic sounds. In this way the students are made to learn the long rhyme in enjoyable way.

When teacher can modulate their voice or tone in appropriate time they will be able to handle the classroom effectively, strong voice teacher have the capacity to handle class effectively.

CONCLUSION

Even though when children are exposed to various knowledge at home they learn the best when they are exposed in classroom. It enhances their interest and make them learn fast As a teacher of diverse learners and with special needs, the teacher must understand that we must provide different pathways for students to demonstrate what they know: reading, writing, speaking, singing, dancing, drawing, and other formats. Incorporating the arts helps ensure that the needs of different types of learners are met.

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